

Managing Editor's Column

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Dear Readers,

It gives me great pleasure to announce the fifth regular issue of 2025. I would like to thank all the authors for their sound research papers and the editorial board and our guest reviewers for their extremely valuable reviews and suggestions for improvement. These contributions and the generous support of the KOALA consortium members enable us to run our journal and maintain its quality. I would also like to thank our broader community for reading and incorporating sound J.UCS papers into their research.

Still, I would like to expand our editorial board: If you are a tenured associate professor or above with a good publication record, please apply to join our editorial board. We are also interested in receiving high-quality proposals for special issues on new topics and emerging trends.

In this regular issue, I am very pleased to introduce 5 papers by 13 authors from 5 countries: Brazil, China, India, Tunisia, Vietnam.

Icaro Prado Fernandes and Luiz Eduardo Galvão Martins from Brazil propose in their article a method to prioritize test cases based on human knowledge using a combination of factors evaluated in an assessment answered by 29 software industry professionals and 5 academics.

Ryma Abassi from Tunisia builds on the principles of ethics, human rights and legal frameworks in his research to address the challenges and dilemmas faced by policymakers when it comes to ensuring cybersecurity without compromising privacy and civil liberties and proposes a set of ethical guidelines and best practices for designing and implementing cybersecurity policies.

M. Priadarsini and J. Akilandeswari from India propose a unique framework in their research that leverages the big five personality traits alongside long short-term memory (LSTM) networks under a multitask learning paradigm to improve the performance of aspect-based sentiment analysis.

Thuy Phuong Khuat, Trang Van and Hoang Thien Van from Vietnam discuss in their research an approach to plant leaf recognition by integrating the vision transformer (ViT) model with the OSSGabor filter, referred to as the OGViT method, and analyze the performance on four public datasets (Swedish Leaf, Flavia, Folio, and UCI Leaf) that outperforms state-of-the-art approaches.

Yang Zhang, Ziwen Wei, Zhihua Liu, Xiaolong Wu and Junchao Qian from China introduce in their study a cost-effective and highly accurate method for recognizing patient postures during radiotherapy based on stacked grayscale 3-channel images.

Enjoy Reading!

Best regards,

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'Christian Gütl', with a stylized flourish at the end.

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